

“Economic Thoughts of Gopal Krishna Gokhale”

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Abstract:

Gopal Krishna Gokhale was a well-known social reformer and political figure in India. He had a number of economic views that attempted to enhance India's economic circumstances. According to Gokhale, the Indian budget ought to be approved item by item and those who are well-versed in Indian circumstances ought to be given a chance to voice their opinions on different spending proposals. He opposed surplus budgets because he thought they would discourage even the most ethical government from engaging in unnecessary spending. Decentralisation of power was something he supported. He recommended setting up punchayats at the village level, followed by district councils and local boards. He believed that significant financial and budgetary issues have to be covered in provincial legislation. Gokhale recommended a few changes to the land revenue structure. He advocated for a fair division of tax money between the federal government, provincial governments and local authorities because he believed that the finances of both local and provincial entities were inadequate. He thought that the path to social and economic advancement lay in education. He recommended that action be taken by the government to encourage trade, especially with foreign nations.

Key Words: Finance, Elementary education, Trade, Decentralisation, Surplus budget.

Introduction:

Gopal Krishna Gokhale was born on 9th May, 1866, into a middle-class family in the Ratnagiri area of contemporary Maharashtra. a moderate politics practitioner who supported the constitutional approach to political activism., He was elected President of the Indian National Congress In 1905. He served as editor of a few well-known periodicals during his lifetime, such as Sarvajanic Sabha's Journal and Sudhakar. In order to teach educated young men, the value of selflessness and to prepare them for public duty, he founded the Servants of India Society in 1905. He did so at Mahatma Gandhi's request and showed a deep interest in the concerns and issues facing labour.

In the precise sense of the word, Gokhale was not a political thinker in the same way as Plato, Aristotle, Locke, and others. He made multiple references to pressing social and economic challenges of the day. His political ideas are centred primarily on socioeconomic problems. He was an outspoken opponent of the caste system and untouchability, a social reformer who supported women's education. As a result, his opinions on nationalism, freedom, and political agenda might be evaluated. He supported independence as a long-term objective, even though it could not be achieved right now. Prioritizing the elimination of wicked societal customs over pursuing freedom from the British was his goal. According to him, a free nation is made up of free people who are not bound by illogical beliefs and superstitions but rather by an informed conscience. Therefore, the "new life movement" should be the name of the new freedom movement.

Objectives:

The aim of this paper is to study the economic thoughts of Mr. Gopal Krishna Gokhale especially on Liberalisation, Decentralisation power, private property rights, Representation for religious minorities, Home Military charges, Indian Finance, Indian agriculture and Elementary education etc.

Methodology:

The paper's focus is on Gopal Krishna Gokhale's socio-economic views and its secondary data came from various books, journals, and other publications.

India's Reactions to British Rule-

Gokhale, like the majority of liberal Indian intellectuals of his age, accepted and valued British rule in India. There were two underlying assumptions to his admiration of British rule and especially to his belief that British authority should continue in India. In the first place, Gokhale shared the conviction of all the moderates that the modernization of Indian society had begun as a result of British rule. The British defended the idea of equality before the law, established representative democracy (although narrowly defined) and protected the right to free speech and the press. These were all new, for sure. Once more, it was the British who initiated India's political integration process. Gokhale said that since Indians had a lot to learn from the British, we should put up with them for a while in order to advance in the fields of business, politics, industry, and education. Gokhale was certain that if British control persisted for a while, India would fully modernize and eventually become a member of the international community, just like any other sovereign state in Europe.

He did not imply that he was entirely pleased with the British government in India when

he defended the continuation of British control in that country. He was, for example, a fierce opponent of the Curzonian administration's haughtiness. In addition, he frequently contended that the British Raj was less British and more raj in that it was hesitant to establish English parliamentary institutions in India. Nevertheless, he thought that British rule was meant to fulfil its providential purpose in India.

Liberalism:

Gokhale was principally a liberal thinker, as was previously mentioned. His brand of liberalism was marginally different from the classical liberalism that ruled Europe in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, though. To fully appreciate the distinctiveness of Gokhale's liberalism, one must get acquainted with liberal philosophy in general.

Gokhale was a liberal who cherished the idea of personal freedom. But liberty, in his view, could only be advantageously allowed when individuals behaved in a way that showed self-control and self-organization. This is not to say that he disapproved of all forms of restraint. He believed that the goal of liberty could not be achieved until citizens were allowed explicit rights to freedom. He felt that press freedom and the right to free speech were essential to achieving the ideal of individual liberty. He opposed the Official Secret Bill in 1904 because he believed it would give the government more power to censor the press.

Decentralization of authority:

Gokhale supported the dispersal of authority, particularly in the area of administration. He primarily intended this to limit the authority of bureaucracy. He was a fervent supporter of giving provincial legislative bodies additional authority to discuss the budget. He argued in testimony before the Hobhouse Decentralization Commission that i) District councils at the intermediate levels ii) Village panchayats at the bottom, or village levels, were essential iii) At the highest level, the Reformed Legislative Councils.

Private Property Rights:

Gokhale was also in favour of contract freedom and the right to private property. "The ordinary citizen is as tenaciously attached to his proprietary rights over his holdings... that there is nothing he will not do if it is in his power to ward off what he regards as a direct or indirect attack on these rights," Bill Gokhale stated in response to comments made on the Land Revenue Code Amendment Bill. It is therefore easy to comprehend why a proposition that would deny him the ability to alienate his holding, when necessary, would seem to him like a very serious infringement on his rights. Gokhale thus upheld the freedom of contract, individual liberty, and private property rights, which together formed the fundamental tenets of liberal doctrine.

To preserve personal freedom and fundamental civic rights, Gokhale suggested that representative institutions be set up in the nation. Gokhale did not, however, call for a universal franchise. He suggested requiring property to be eligible for enfranchisement. For instance, Gokhale wished that only those who had paid a minimum amount of land revenue would be eligible to vote in the village Panchayat elections.

Representation for religious minorities:

Furthermore, he proposed the idea of special representation for religious minorities. Gokhale argued for distinct representation for Muslims, acknowledging the sectarian divide between Muslims and Hindus. Thus, Gokhale was a liberal who supported the creation of representative institutions in a limited sense while also standing up for the idea of individual liberty. Gokhale held very different views on the **state's role** than did classical liberalism. A laissez-faire state is advocated by classical liberalism. Classical liberalism limits the state's powers to those of law enforcement. They think the best kind of government is one that governs as little as possible. However, Gokhale, in the footsteps of Justice M.G. Ranade, argued that government action was necessary to control the nation's social and economic life. In this regard, Gokhale was very different from J.S. Mill. Gokhale advocated for government intervention in the economy to promote agricultural and industrial growth. In addition to the distribution mechanisms, he desired government intervention in the production process.

Gokhale said that Indians required a government that prioritizes their welfare over all other concerns and portrays the injustices meted out to them elsewhere as genuine offers to Englishmen and which makes every effort to advance the material and moral interests of people both inside and outside of India. Therefore, rather than just functioning as a police state, Gokhale contends, the government must to take part in welfare programs and when necessary, get involved in the country's economic problems. It argued for required state intervention in the nation's social and economic affairs while simultaneously rejecting extreme individualism and highlighting the detrimental effects of liberty.

Home Military charges:

Those who suggested readjusting financial arrangements in order to secure a decrease in taxpayer loads and a more effective use of the resources that are available. This category included the lowering of military costs, the adjusting of land valuations, etc. He pointed out that Home Military charges increasing continuously since 1862. It was only two millions sterling which grown up to five millions in 1893.

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Indian Finance:

Any specific economic strategy that worked for England might not work for India as well. Ranade supported government interference in the nation's economy since the British administrators' free trade and open competition policies did not encourage the development of industrialization in India. Gokhale conducted a thorough analysis of Indian finance between 1874 and 1909, breaking the time period up into four phases and contrasting the rise in spending with the rise in revenue. Gokhale came to the conclusion that it was necessary to maintain a balance between revenue and expenditure based on his studies, which showed that expenditure increase tended to outpace revenue growth. Furthermore, having a surplus budget made little sense while the average person's budget was unable to balance itself. In an era of fiscal excess, Gokhale suggested the following actions be taken by the government: i) Establishing a million-pound fund to relieve Indian farmers of their mountain of debt ii) The establishment of agricultural banks based on the Egyptian model, which would activate cooperative credit societies. iii) Supporting industrial and technical education and authorizing higher spending for this reason. iv) Free and required elementary education. v) Enhancement of local bodies' financial situation.

The aforementioned recommendations made by Gokhale make it clear that he believed having a surplus budget was useless when the average person's budget was unable to balance itself. There should be an excess budget, it must be allocated towards advancing the state's development functions. Gokhale supported the Swadeshi cause in addition to opposing the government's fiscal policies. He did not associate the boycott with Swadeshi, though. He saw the Swadeshi movement as an economic and nationalistic one. In terms of its patriotic side, it represented fidelity to the homeland but also migration toward its spouse. It made sure that products made in the nation were quickly consumed and provided a constant boost to output by maintaining the demand for local goods.

Indian agriculture:

Gokhale was also informed on the situation of Indian agriculture. He saw that there was a low

crop yield per acre and a severe downturn in India's agriculture sector. In these conditions, he objected to the state's demand for an increase in land revenue. He was very clear in saying that he thought the indirect taxes and land revenue together put an intolerable burden on the poor. In order to ensure agricultural success, he wanted the state to prioritize scientific agriculture and irrigation. He felt that the excise duty on cotton textiles was unfair as it was, in his view, established to offset the import levies. Gokhale believed the poor were already burdened by this kind of task. According to Gokhale, the government ought to support society's progressive factions. As a result, he backed the motion on the Civil Marriage Bill. With the backing of a powerful and enlightened minority, Gokhale desired that the state moves forward with social transformation initiatives.

Elementary education:

Gokhale recommended universal elementary education that is free and required. For him, receiving an elementary education was more than just learning how to read and write. It implied increased moral and financial efficiency on the part of the individual, which is why he worked so hard to push for free public education. He also recommended banning alcohol and taking other steps to improve public health in order to remove obstacles and hardships from the way that a person's personality develops.

Once the government has given its approval, the local authority will put the rule into effect. Local bodies were supposed to have the authority to impose coercion throughout or in portions of the territory they were responsible for. In order to pay for free and mandatory elementary education, local governments were also to be granted the authority to impose taxes.

- Guardians with incomes under rupees 10 were not to be required to pay fees.
- Girls should have to attend primary school.
- Enforcing compulsory primary education for boys aged six to ten is a good idea.
- The guardians who fail to send their children to authorized primary schools must face consequences.

Trade:

He supported trade protection as a means of fostering the expansion of the Indian economy. Gokhale took issue with free trade doctrine. It is obvious that Gokhale was an Indian in the truest meaning of the word based on an evaluation of his contributions to the many fields. His actions and words were always directed towards improving the economic circumstances of the majority of Indians.

Self-Reliance:

Gokhale advocated for self-sufficiency and self-reliance across the economy to lessen dependency on imports and boost homegrown companies.

Gokhale said that railways are being used more and more to send food grains and raw materials to other countries and to import goods from other countries and this is causing damage to indigenous industries. The expansion of railways in India is thought to be primarily for the exploitation of Indians.

Conclusion:

Gopal Krishna Gokhale was a social reformer who believed in a constitutional approach to political activism. He was a supporter of women's education and an advocate for socioeconomic issues. He saw independence as a long-term goal, putting an end to evil social practices before seeking independence from the British. In his view, an informed conscience, rather than irrational beliefs and superstitions, binds the citizens of a free nation. Thus, the new freedom movement needs to be known as the "new life movement." He supported the decentralization of government, the fair distribution of tax income, and the advancement of trade and education. His thoughts were centered on India's economic growth and the well-being of its citizens.

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